

ISOLATION OF LUPEOL FROM *ASTERACANTHA LONGIFOLIA* NEES

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Lupeol has been isolated from the roots of *Asteracantha longifolia* Nees.

The roots and leaves of *Asteracantha longifolia* Nees (N.O. *Acanthaceae*) (Ghatak, and Dutta, this *Journal*, 1931, 8, 23; Basu and Ghode, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1952, 14, 212; Chopra, Ghosh and Ratnagiriswaran, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1934, 22, 268), also known as *Hygrophila spinosa* (Beng. *Kuliakhara*), possess medicinal values and are reported to be effective in curing rheumatism and urinary infections. From the roots of this plant the present investigators isolated a triterpenoid alcohol (A), subsequently identified as lupeol, in a good yield (0.25%) besides two other non-alkaloidal minor compounds, melting at 245-47° and 153-55° respectively.*

The separation of these three constituents was possible through a Tswett column. Lupeol which analysed for $C_{30}H_{50}O$, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +27.9$ (in chloroform) responded to sterol reactions, decolorised bromine in chloroform solution, formed a monoacetyl ($C_{30}H_{48}O.CO.CH_3$, m.p. 213°) and a monobenzoyl derivative ($C_{30}H_{48}O.C_6H_5$, m.p. 256°). Its I.R. spectrum (in chloroform) exhibited the absorption peaks at 2965 cm^{-1} for -OH, 1382 cm^{-1} for $\overset{|}{\underset{|}{C}}.CH_3$, at 1360 cm^{-1} for *gem*-dimethyl, 916 and 984, and 889 cm^{-1} for $-CH=CH_2$ and at 1630 cm^{-1} for $-\overset{|}{C}=\overset{|}{C}-$ grouping.

Difficulties were encountered in assessing the precise molecular formula to lupeol (from C and H analyses and molecular weight determination by the method of Rast) and thus in identifying this sample. It was therefore intended to study its desoxy derivative, *i.e.* the corresponding hydrocarbon for characterising the substance. The latter was prepared by the Wolff-Krishner reduction (Barton, Ives and Thomas, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2056) of the ketone obtained from the parent compound by chromic acid oxidation according to the method of Sarett *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1707). The above ketone and the hydrocarbon were incidentally found to be identical with lupenone and α -lupene, as evidenced from a direct comparison of their molecular formulae, properties and infra-red spectra. Further confirmation about their identities was available from a direct comparison of the ketone and the hydrocarbon prepared from the triterpenoid alcohol (A) with authentic samples of lupenone and α -lupene (Heilbron *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1583; 1938, 329). Further isolation and characterisation of the minor components (*loc. cit.*) are in progress. The chloroform and alcoholic extracts of the roots were investigated for alkaloids without any promising results.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of Lupeol.—Air-dried powdered roots (900 g.) were Soxhletted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) for 24 hours and the extract was concentrated. The

* A note on "Chemical investigation of *Asteracantha longifolia* Nees" was published by the authors in the Proceedings of the 44th Indian Science Congress, 1957, Part III, p. 128.

latter deposited a semi-solid green mass when kept in the frigidaire for a couple of weeks. A portion of this crude material (M) (0.3 g.) was dissolved in benzene and subjected to chromatographic separation through Brockmann alumina (37 cm x 2 cm) using benzene and later a mixture of benzene and ethyl acetate (4:1) as developers. Eluates were collected in fractions of 15 c.c. (Table I).

TABLE I

Eluents	Fractions.	Residue on evaporation
Benzene	1-5	Non-crystallisable yellow oil
"	6	Solid, m.p. 170-80°
"	7	Solid, m.p. 205°
"	8-14	Solid, m.p. 208°
"	15-18	Nil
"	19-20	Solid, m.p. 151-55
"	21-23	Nil
Benzene-ethyl acetate (4:1)	24	Nil
"	25-27	Solid, m.p. 246°
"	28-30	Nil

Fractions (7-14) containing lupeol crystallised from rectified spirit in long needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 212-13°. The yield was about 0.25% on the basis of the weight of dry roots. $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +27.9$ (in chloroform). (Found: C, 84.28; H, 11.6. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{48}O$: C, 84.5; H, 11.7%).

Acetyl Derivative of Lupeol.—Lupeol (0.5 g.) was mixed up with acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) and refluxed in an oil-bath at 135-40° for 3 hours with 3 to 4 drops of dry pyridine. The reaction product was poured into ice-cold-water, stirred and recrystallised from rectified spirit. On repeated crystallisation from the same solvent the acetyl derivative was obtained pure, m.p. 213°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +46.9$ (in chloroform). (Found: C, 82.21; H, 11.34. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{46}O.COCH_3$: C, 82.05; H, 11.11%). The sample showed no depression in melting point on admixture with an authentic sample of lupeol acetate which alone melted at 213°.

Benzoyl Derivative of Lupeol.—Lupeol (0.4 g.), benzoyl chloride (5 c.c.) and dry pyridine (0.5 c.c.) were mixed and refluxed in an oil-bath for 2 hours at 140°. The reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold-water (50 c.c.), stirred continuously and filtered. The residue was washed several times with boiling water. The product was purified by repeated crystallisations from rectified spirit, m.p. 256°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +61.2$ (in chloroform). (Found: C, 84.02; H, 10.23. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{46}O.CO.C_6H_5$: C, 83.77; H, 10.18%). The mixed melting point of this benzoyl derivative and lupeol benzoate, m.p. 256°, remained unchanged.

Lupenone.—Lupeol (1.15 g.) was dissolved in pyridine (11.5 c.c.) and mixed with a solution containing pyridine (11.5 c.c.) and chromium trioxide (1.15 g.). The whole mixture was kept overnight at room temperature and then poured into water and extracted with benzene. The benzene layer was washed with water, dried and

concentrated. The product, lupenone, was purified by chromatography and finally by crystallisation from rectified spirit, m.p. 170° ; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +63^{\circ}.5$ (in chloroform). (Found: C, 84.82; H, 11.12. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{48}O$: C, 84.90; H, 11.34%).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of lupenone was obtained by refluxing an alcoholic solution of lupenone with Brady's reagent on a water-bath. Yellow crystals of D.N.P., m.p. $204-205^{\circ}$, appeared after half-an-hour. It recrystallised from a mixture of rectified spirit and ethyl acetate (2:1). (Found: C, 71.49; H, 8.58; N, 9.24. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{32}O_4N_4$: C, 71.52; H, 8.60; N, 9.27%).

Reduction of Lupenone to α -Lupene.—The latter was prepared by refluxing a mixture of lupenone (0.4 g.) with hydrazine (1 c.c.), diethyleneglycol (15 c.c.) and sodium (1.0 g.) in an oil-bath at $180-200^{\circ}$ for 12 hours in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The reaction product was poured into water and extracted with benzene (300 c.c. in three instalments). The benzene extract was concentrated and purified by passing through a Tswett-column using Brockmann alumina as an adsorbent and subsequently by several crystallisations from ethanol. α -Lupene melted at $161-63^{\circ}$; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +30^{\circ}.4$ (in chloroform). (Found: C, 87.78; H, 12.05. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}$: C, 87.80; H, 12.19%).

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